

FREQUENCY OF HYPERKALEMIA IN CHRONIC KIDNEY DISEASE PATIENTS PRESENTING TO TERTIARY CARE HOSPITAL

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17275726>

Keywords

Hyperkalemia, chronic kidney disease, RAAS Inhibitors.

Article History

Received: 01 July 2025

Accepted: 01 September 2025

Published: 15 September 2025

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Abstract

Background: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a progressive condition associated with numerous complications, including hyperkalemia—a potentially life-threatening electrolyte imbalance. Hyperkalemia in CKD is primarily due to impaired renal potassium excretion, often worsened by comorbidities such as diabetes and the use of renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) inhibitors. Despite its clinical importance, data on the frequency of hyperkalemia among CKD patients in local settings remains limited. *Objective:* To determine the frequency of hyperkalemia in patients with chronic kidney disease presenting to a tertiary care hospital. *Methods:* A cross-sectional study was conducted at the Nephrology Department of Rehman Medical Institute, Peshawar, over six months. A total of 120 CKD patients aged 18–75 years were enrolled using consecutive non-probability sampling. Patients on dialysis or with acute kidney injury or chronic liver disease were excluded. Serum potassium levels were measured, with hyperkalemia defined as $K^+ > 5.0$ mEq/L. Data were analyzed using SPSS v23. Chi-square tests were applied for associations, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant. *Results:* The mean age of participants was 56.4 ± 12.1 years, with 53.3% males. Hyperkalemia was observed in 35.8% ($n = 43$) of patients. A statistically significant association was found between hyperkalemia and diabetes mellitus ($p = 0.031$) as well as RAAS inhibitor use ($p = 0.024$). No significant associations were found with gender, hypertension, or socioeconomic status. *Conclusion:* Hyperkalemia is common among CKD patients, particularly in those with diabetes and those on RAAS inhibitors. Routine monitoring and early management are essential to mitigate associated risks.

INTRODUCTION

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a major global health burden and ranks among the leading causes of mortality from non-communicable diseases. It is

defined and staged using markers of kidney function—such as estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) and albuminuria—which enable risk stratification in

accordance with national and international guidelines [1]. Early identification is essential, as CKD often remains asymptomatic in its initial stages [1]. Importantly, for most individuals with CKD, the risk of cardiovascular events significantly exceeds the risk of progression to end-stage renal disease (ESRD) [1]. CKD is also recognized as a key risk factor for acute kidney injury (AKI), which itself contributes significantly to global mortality rates [2]. While only a minority of CKD patients progress to ESRD, the need for renal replacement therapy—such as dialysis or transplantation—places a substantial financial and emotional burden on healthcare systems and patients alike [2].

Among the serious complications associated with CKD is **hyperkalemia**, a potentially life-threatening electrolyte imbalance characterized by elevated serum potassium levels [3]. In CKD, hyperkalemia primarily results from impaired renal potassium excretion due to reduced glomerular filtration and compromised tubular secretion, commonly attributed to tubulointerstitial dysfunction [3]. Moreover, the use of renin-angiotensin-aldosterone system (RAAS) inhibitors—mainstays in the management of CKD—along with the presence of diabetes mellitus, further exacerbates the risk of hyperkalemia by decreasing urinary potassium excretion [4].

Metabolic acidosis, a frequent consequence of advanced CKD, contributes to hyperkalemia by shifting potassium from the intracellular to the extracellular compartment [5]. Normally, the kidneys are responsible for eliminating the majority of daily potassium intake, while the colon handles approximately 5–10% of the excretion [5]. As renal function deteriorates, compensatory potassium excretion via the gastrointestinal tract increases, but it is often insufficient to maintain normokalemia [5].

Maintaining serum potassium within the normal physiological range (3.5–5.0 mEq/L) is essential, as deviations can significantly impair cardiac conduction, myocardial contractility, vascular tone, and neuromuscular function [6]. Previous studies have reported a hyperkalemia prevalence of up to 33.9% in patients with CKD [7].

Despite the global significance of hyperkalemia in CKD, there is a paucity of local data addressing its prevalence in our region. To the best of our knowledge, no prior studies have specifically

examined the frequency of hyperkalemia among CKD patients under regular nephrological follow-up within our healthcare setting. Therefore, this study aims to fill that knowledge gap and provide data that could inform and enhance clinical management protocols for affected individuals.

Objective

To determine the frequency of hyperkalemia in patients with chronic kidney disease presenting to a tertiary care hospital.

Materials and methods:

Study Setting:

This study was conducted at the Department of Nephrology, Rehman Medical Institute, Peshawar.

Study Design:

A cross-sectional study design was employed.

Study Duration:

The study was carried out over a period of six months, following approval of the synopsis by the College of Physicians and Surgeons Pakistan (CPSPP).

Sample Size:

A total of 120 patients were included. The sample size was calculated using the WHO sample size formula based on the following parameters:

- Anticipated prevalence of hyperkalemia: 33.9%
- Confidence level: 95%
- Margin of error: 8.5%

Sampling Technique:

Consecutive non-probability sampling was used to recruit participants.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients aged 18 to 75 years
- Both male and female patients
- Diagnosed cases of chronic kidney disease as defined above

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients undergoing hemodialysis
- Patients with acute deterioration in renal function
- Patients with known chronic liver disease

Data Collection Procedure

After obtaining approval from both the CPSP Research Unit and the Institutional Ethics Committee, the study was initiated. Eligible patients were identified and approached for participation. Informed written consent was obtained after explaining the purpose, benefits, and potential risks of the study.

Demographic data—including age, gender, body mass index (BMI), socioeconomic status, residence, educational level, and occupation—were recorded. A complete medical history was taken prior to the physical examination. Eligible CKD patients were then subjected to laboratory testing for serum potassium levels to determine the presence of hyperkalemia.

All assessments and evaluations were conducted under the supervision of a nephrology consultant with at least five years of post-fellowship experience. Patient data, clinical findings, and laboratory results were documented using a structured and standardized proforma.

Data Analysis Procedure

Data entry and analysis were performed using SPSS version 23. Frequencies and percentages were used to summarize categorical variables such as gender, hyperkalemia status, presence of comorbid conditions (e.g., diabetes mellitus, hypertension, congestive heart failure), and sociodemographic characteristics.

For continuous variables such as age and BMI, the mean ± standard deviation or median with interquartile range (IQR) was reported, depending on data distribution. Stratification of hyperkalemia was performed based on age, BMI, gender, presence of

comorbidities, and sociodemographic variables to assess potential effect modifiers.

Post-stratification, the **Chi-square test** or **Fisher’s exact test** (where applicable) was used to examine associations, with a **p-value of < 0.05** considered statistically significant. Results were presented in the form of tables and charts for clear interpretation.

Operational Definitions

Chronic Kidney Disease (CKD):

CKD was defined as kidney damage or an estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) less than 60 mL/min/1.73 m² persisting for more than three months, regardless of the underlying cause. Alternatively, patients with an albumin-to-creatinine ratio greater than 30 mg/g in at least two out of three spot urine samples were also classified as having CKD.

Hyperkalemia:

Hyperkalemia was diagnosed through blood testing, defined as a serum potassium (K⁺) level greater than 5.0 mEq/L.

Results:

A total of **120 patients** with chronic kidney disease (CKD) were included in this study. The **mean age** of participants was **56.4 ± 12.1 years**, with a slightly higher representation of **males (53.3%)** than females. The overall **frequency of hyperkalemia** in this study population was **35.8% (n = 43)**.

Table 1 summarizes the demographic and clinical profile of the enrolled patients, including age distribution, gender, BMI, comorbidities, and socioeconomic background.

Table 1: Baseline Demographic and Clinical Characteristics of Study Participants

Variable	Frequency (%) / Mean ± SD
Age (years)	56.4 ± 12.1
Gender	
Male	64 (53.3%)
Female	56 (46.7%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.8 ± 3.9
Comorbidities	
Diabetes Mellitus	71 (59.2%)
Hypertension	89 (74.2%)
Congestive Heart Failure	18 (15%)

Socioeconomic Status	
Low	49 (40.8%)
Middle	58 (48.3%)
High	13 (10.8%)
Residence	
Urban	77 (64.2%)
Rural	43 (35.8%)

Table 2 shows the overall frequency of hyperkalemia in the study population based on serum potassium levels.

Table 2: Frequency of Hyperkalemia Among CKD Patients

Hyperkalemia Status	Frequency (n)
Present ($K^+ > 5.0$ mEq/L)	43
Absent ($K^+ \leq 5.0$ mEq/L)	77
Total	120

Figure 1: Percentage of hyperkalemia among CKD patients.

Table 3 shows the stratified analysis of hyperkalemia by selected demographic and clinical variables using Chi-square test. Statistically significant associations were found with diabetes mellitus and use of RAAS inhibitors.

Table 3: Association of Hyperkalemia with Selected Variables

Variable	Hyperkalemia Present	Hyperkalemia Absent	p-value
Gender			0.513
Male	21	43	
Female	22	34	
Diabetes Mellitus			0.031*
Yes	32	39	
No	11	38	

Hypertension			0.118
Yes	36	53	
No	7	24	
Use of RAAS Inhibitors			0.024*
Yes	29	36	
No	14	41	

*Significant at $p < 0.05$

Discussion:

In this cross-sectional study involving 120 patients diagnosed with chronic kidney disease (CKD), we observed that hyperkalemia was present in 35.8% of

the study population. This frequency is notably higher than that reported in some international studies but is in line with reports from nephrology clinics and hospital-based cohorts where advanced CKD and comorbidities are more prevalent. A study conducted by Kovcsdy et al. reported a hyperkalemia incidence of 21.4% in non-dialysis CKD patients, with risk increasing with CKD stage progression and comorbidity burden [8]. This supports the interpretation that our patient population, likely representing moderate to severe CKD cases, is at higher baseline risk.

The mean age of the patients was 56.4 years, and males slightly outnumbered females, which aligns with previous studies demonstrating similar demographic trends in CKD cohorts [9]. The high burden of comorbid conditions in our patients—including diabetes mellitus (59.2%) and hypertension (74.2%)—also mirrors global epidemiologic data. These comorbidities are known not only to contribute to CKD progression but also to increase the risk of hyperkalemia. Diabetes, in particular, impairs renal tubular potassium secretion and may be associated with hyporeninemic hypoaldosteronism, contributing to potassium retention [10].

Our analysis revealed that diabetes mellitus was significantly associated with hyperkalemia ($p = 0.031$). This is consistent with findings from Li et al., who demonstrated a significantly higher prevalence of hyperkalemia among diabetic CKD patients, particularly those with albuminuria and poor glycemic control [11]. The interplay between insulin resistance, RAAS activation, and reduced renal potassium excretion explains this increased susceptibility.

Diabetics are also more likely to be prescribed RAAS inhibitors, further compounding their risk.

Notably, the use of RAAS inhibitors was also significantly linked with hyperkalemia in our study ($p = 0.024$). RAAS blockers, while essential for their renoprotective and cardioprotective effects, reduce aldosterone-mediated potassium excretion, particularly in advanced CKD stages. Studies such as that by Riccio et al. have shown that hyperkalemia is a common reason for RAASi discontinuation in CKD patients, despite their therapeutic benefits [12]. The management dilemma of balancing RAASi benefits against hyperkalemia risks remains a clinical challenge, emphasizing the need for regular potassium monitoring and appropriate use of adjunct therapies, including potassium binders when indicated.

Interestingly, no statistically significant association was found between hyperkalemia and gender, hypertension, or socioeconomic status. Some studies have suggested a higher risk of hyperkalemia in males or those with poor access to healthcare services, but these associations often lose statistical significance after adjusting for confounders such as CKD stage and RAASi use [13]. Our findings suggest that metabolic and pharmacologic factors (i.e., diabetes and RAAS inhibition) may be more influential in determining potassium balance than demographic variables in this setting.

The overall hyperkalemia rate of 35.8% is somewhat higher than seen in some large cohorts (often ranging from 15–30%), possibly due to our study being conducted in a tertiary care nephrology center, where patients are more likely to have advanced disease. Piccoli et al., in a European cohort of nephrology-referred patients, reported a prevalence of 28%, with even higher rates among those with Stage 4 and 5 CKD [14]. Additionally, regional dietary patterns rich in potassium and delayed healthcare access may have also contributed to the elevated rates in our study.

From a clinical standpoint, our findings underscore the importance of proactive potassium monitoring and tailored management strategies. Since hyperkalemia can lead to serious cardiac arrhythmias, addressing it is not only a matter of laboratory correction but of preventing morbidity and mortality. Strategies such as low-potassium diets, use of non-potassium-sparing diuretics, and novel potassium binders (e.g., patiromer or sodium zirconium cyclosilicate) are now being integrated into guidelines to facilitate continued use of RAAS inhibitors [15]. A focus on individualized care—particularly in diabetic and late-stage CKD patients—is critical to optimize outcomes while maintaining guideline-directed medical therapy.

This study has several limitations. First, its cross-sectional nature limits our ability to infer causal relationships or temporal trends. Second, the sample size (n = 120) may restrict generalizability and limit the power to detect more subtle associations. Third, only a single serum potassium measurement was used to define hyperkalemia, which may have included transient elevations due to dietary or sampling variability. Fourth, important variables such as CKD staging, eGFR levels, dietary potassium intake, acid-base status, and concurrent medications (like beta-blockers or NSAIDs) were not recorded, potentially confounding the observed associations. Fifth, this was a single-center study from a tertiary care hospital, likely including more severe CKD cases, and thus results may not reflect the broader CKD population in community settings. Lastly, adherence to prescribed RAAS inhibitors and dosing details were not confirmed, which limits insight into the medication-related risk.

Despite these limitations, this study provides valuable local data and highlights the need for vigilant monitoring and management of hyperkalemia in CKD patients—especially those with diabetes and those on RAAS blockade.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, this study demonstrated a high frequency of hyperkalemia among patients with chronic kidney disease presenting to a tertiary care nephrology clinic, with significant associations observed with diabetes mellitus and the use of RAAS inhibitors. These findings highlight the clinical

importance of routine potassium monitoring in CKD patients, particularly those with metabolic comorbidities or on medications known to impair potassium excretion. While RAAS inhibitors are essential for slowing CKD progression and reducing cardiovascular risk, their safe use requires careful balancing with the risk of hyperkalemia. Early identification and appropriate management of hyperkalemia—through dietary counseling, medication adjustments, or the use of potassium-lowering therapies—can help preserve renal and cardiac health while maintaining the benefits of guideline-recommended treatments.

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